

STATEMENT OF MOTIVATION

Research Proposal - Nexus Between Indoor Air Quality and Phytoremediation: Deploying Gm Plants Route in Domestic Spaces

I come from a clime where fuel poverty, low GDP, ineffectual housing policies and conflict are rife. Housing is a challenge while gentrification is putting pressure on relatively better-designed settlements for access to social amenities. Settlements that are subsisting in many climes are populated by occupants that have a lot of social, financial and economic challenges. Coupled with fuel poverty, ravages of the Covid-19 pandemic, cultural practices and challenges of climate change, most of these settlements are inundated with biogenic and anthropogenic emissions like BVOCs, PM_{2.5}, tropospheric ozone, NO_x and SO₂. This issue is worsened by high occupant density evident in most of these settlements as many individuals are constrained to occupy few spaces due to housing deficit. Worst case scenario came into effect when families lived out there lives in several types of lockdowns. Menial jobs, chores including cooking and sundry domestic activities were done in spaces in close proximity to homes while some were done within the same living quarters. To this end, there was relative spike in the pollution concentration values (PCVs) of BVOCs, particulate matter and amplification sites. Most spaces in these semi-planned and unplanned settlements do not meet up with proper design ethics as they lacked proper fenestration and orientation. Previous studies done have also identified that certain BVOCs like isoprene, monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes are precursors of tropospheric ozone. The atmospheric reaction between isoprene and NO_x in the presence of sunlight produces tropospheric O₃ and secondary organic aerosols which also contribute their own quota in affecting the overall health of occupants. It is on record that tropospheric O₃, apart from affecting crop yield, also disrupt the delicate balance between oxygen-carbon dioxide exchange efficiency of the red blood corpuscles making it difficult for vulnerable populations like children and asthma patients to have challenges with their health. Over-exposure to NO_x predisposes individuals to cancer and could be fatal to children. BVOCs like isoprene is denser than air and has sufficient inflammability. Generally, an outdoor emission, isoprene can make ingress into indoor spaces through wind draughts and transient pollution clouds. We also have the likelihood of the fact that humans also exhale isoprene. With high occupant density and the fact that a 72kg individual exhales 17 milligrams of isoprene daily, this anthro-metabolic emission becomes an issue as more people will be inundating the indoor space with BVOCs. This researcher will seek to understudy these pollutants, know the extent of their preponderance from cultural pulsations, chart their flow pattern through computational fluid dynamics and attempt to calibrate them. Efforts will also be made to see how we can effectively adopt bioremediation processes to mitigate indoor air pollution. This is possible by working with the simulation charts of our CFDs and locate areas of viscous nullity. At these places, this researcher intends situating certain houseplants that have effective translocation and accumulation properties. Through this bioremediation process, we can attempt to use 'green infrastructure' as nature-based solutions. Such green infrastructure will be altered; changing their genome and DNA structure to positively influence their capacity to improve IAQ. This study will not only improve air-scrubbing capability of these GM plants, it will also investigate the possibility of fronting GM plants with very minimal propensity to exude biogenic emissions.

This applicant has engaged actively as a research assistant for previous Ph.D. scholars in the genre of Built Environment. I have taken part in socio-technical negotiation sessions with lead researchers as a prelude to the

handling of data-capturing devices. Thereafter, I have participated in interactive sessions with study populations and went ahead to handle and plant data loggers. In research studies that I have led, I have undertaken case studies of sample sites, recorded and observed data as the case may be. Structured questionnaires, as designed and administered under the supervision of my supervisors are also my strong highlights. Right now, am conducting a study on the composite design of an active sump for riverine areas of my community. This study commenced in June, 2022 at the Egbeada Housing Layout of Imo state, Nigeria. This self-sponsored research study is currently going on with my trained research assistants who I endeavoured to train in data sampling, field studies, population stratification and handling of data recorders.

I have extensive experience of research dispensation in housing, IAQ, sustainability indices and IAP and have authored publications – conference presentations and journal entries - on them. My academic pursuits have always had derivations from thematic concepts of a sustainable environment with the occupant as the ultimate benefactor. From my HND, B.Sc. and M.Sc. pursuits, I have always aligned with any conversation that is designed to make our living cocoons safer and more resilient towards the health and wellbeing of the occupant.

I took my decision to pitch tent with Victoria University of Wellington because of its sterling indices in research dispensation. In fact, this is why I keep on putting in my applications with the hope that I would be part of this noble institution that has quite an appreciable number of patents in its kitty. Also, research at Victoria University of Wellington is impeccable in ranking of its eight research strengths. Of particular interest to me is the university's knack for high-quality research methodologies. This is the reason why I believe that my research into bioremediation of indoor environments will receive maximum support in bench research and laboratory appurtenances if conducted within the institution with its unique partnership with Google and NASA. In my recent applications with the Victoria University of Wellington, I have found out that they need the best and well-prepared proposals for sponsorship. This is another reason why I have kept faith with the pedigree of excellence shown by this institution and which I must endeavor to emulate. Its propensity to attract nearly \$70million in external research funding is one of the reasons I have seriously rejigged my proposal to be worth scholarship funding. I am of the utmost belief and expectation that my proposal would still be found relevant for funding by the Victoria University of Wellington as their zero tolerance on shoddy applications is definitely above par.

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